

ISic3466

I.Sicily inscription 3466

Language

Latin

Type**Material**

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Gaulus

Place of origin (modern)

Gozo

Provenance

Victoria-Rabat, found during the replacement of the altar in the Church of S. George, 31 October 1760

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Unknown

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR113441

1. Aur(eli-)[]L []

2. QVAV[]I []

3. GINTAGI []

4. CALENI []

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285170

EDR 113441

EDCS 22100629

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7510 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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